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THE MAIN ISSUES AND PROBLEMS OF URBAN PLANNING AT THE PRESENT TIME.

Shaharsozlikning hozirgi zamondagi asosiy masalalari va muammolari.

Rasul Achildiyev¹

¹*Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: In the age of the current technical revolution, the reverse issue, i.e. preservation, restoration and health of nature is a vital necessity for man. City and nature, man and nature are synonymous concepts for this architect. They require the architect to have a philosophical approach to his work, because the architect is the leading figure in establishing unity between man and nature. The design of cities in Uzbekistan is based on the principle of the most expedient placement of residential buildings and industrial enterprises, providing sanitary and hygienic distances, organizing convenient transport connections. It is intended to bring nature closer to people by creating parks in and around cities, expanding forests, creating water bodies, etc.

Key words: Urbanization, urban development, transport, noise, environmental pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Human life takes place in the environment, which broadly includes architecture and nature. Their mutual harmony is a necessary condition for human activity. Comfortable and beautiful cities, architectural ensembles, industrial and residential complexes, agricultural facilities, natural landscape are the environment that is comfortable for a person. The influence of the environment created on a person is multifaceted. It includes not only the material side of life, but also the spiritual side. Clean air, the expediency and beauty of architecture, the comfort of a residential building - all this has a positive effect on a person, and on the contrary, unsightly residential areas, lack of greenery, air and river pollution has a negative effect on the psyche. People have been living with nature for centuries. Building houses from soil, stone and oil wells, planting crops, digging minerals from the ground - all this is the use of natural resources, and at the same time, it is the destruction of nature. [1] [2]

Thus, protection of nature and appropriate, economical use of its resources is one of the main issues of modern urban planning.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Urban planning is a theory and practice of planning and construction of urban and residential areas that solve socio-economic, sanitary-hygienic, engineering, transport and architectural-artistic issues together.

The socio-economic issue is solved by choosing a population settlement system, taking into account the future of urban and rural development, economic effective use of natural and territorial resources, population growth, and the organization of optimal cultural and household services for the population.

Sanitary-hygienic issues include creating healthy conditions for the life of the population, defining a sanitary-protective zone between industrial and residential districts, landscaping, fighting against pollution of soil, air and water (water bodies)

and noise. In regions with a hot climate, the issues of creating an optimal microclimate of the external environment, installing sun protection devices, placing buildings in the necessary direction, insolation, drying or beautifying the areas, and using the beneficial wind direction are solved. [2]

Technical construction issues include studying the engineering-geological conditions of the areas selected for the construction of residential areas, determining the level of construction techniques and modern means, solving the rational system of transport and pedestrian connections, engineering preparation and engineering improvement of the areas (drinking water supply, wastewater treatment conduit, hot water, cold water, gas and electricity supply, etc.) and so on. [3]

Architectural-artistic issues are related to determining the general architectural structure of the city, street and branch street networks, solving the functional structure of individual parts of the city, including solving the composition of the center. These issues are resolved taking into account the local natural climatic features (relief, landscape, water bodies, green fields, etc.), national traditions of life, historical and cultural monuments of the people. Their joint approach to solving these issues is one of the main conditions of urban development.

The process of development of cities is complex and multifaceted. It is impossible to take into account all its small details. But the main direction of this process should be taken into account at the initial stage of design. The lack of vision for the future can be explained by the fact that many cities' capital markets are not viable. That's why they wear out quickly. [2] [3] (Achilidiyev, R. M., & Otabekova, D. (2022). Yirik shaharlarda

transport muammolarini hal etishda xorijiy tajribalar. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(11), 496-502.)

Today we can think about 21st century architecture. This is important not only for the future, but also for our current practice.

Modern architecture is not only an art, but also a unity of science and technology. There is no art that combines the achievements of many branches of knowledge in an architecturally superior way. Here, the use of powerful computers is required to solve the complex problems of modern urban planning.

It is impossible to understand, evaluate and solve the problems of cities within the framework of knowledge. The study and design of cities requires the integration of approaches and perspectives of different disciplines, understanding the city as a phenomenon of the modern world. The constant growth of large cities and agglomerations everywhere forces us to think about the internal laws and reasons of these phenomena, to identify the shortcomings of such forms of population settlement and to evaluate their real costs.

Important disadvantages of large cities and large agglomerations are known:

- increase in the cost of engineering equipment;
- increasing cost of transport problems;
- environmental pollution;
- alienation of the population of big cities from nature;
- psycho-physiological consequences (not yet fully studied) and others.

In addition, large cities "suck" production forces from medium and small cities.

There is a concept of "French desert" in French urbanism and geographical literature. This means that the life force of the whole country will be attracted to the Paris agglomeration. Nevertheless, the effect of gathering a large part of the population together in one place, which creates a huge economic, scientific and intellectual potential, is very large and stimulates the growth of cities. Large cities have resources for the rapid mobilization of productive forces. Here there are great opportunities for the cooperation of industry, science and higher education, implementation of administrative, organizational and distribution functions. There are a wide variety of services for the population with a high level of living culture.

Thus, in the development of large cities and urban agglomerations, it is possible to use their advantages and reduce their disadvantages. Before solving these issues, let's analyze the question of whether the big cities of the 20th century are actually more inconvenient to live in than the cities of the past.

Historical sources testify that problems such as traffic, noise, environmental pollution existed in the past. For example: In the reign of Queen Elizabeth, coal burning was banned in London, and it was punished. It can be seen that transport and environmental problems are not only dependent on urban growth, but also on the social, economic, technical and technological means available in the society to solve them. [1] [2]

Today's largest cities are cleaner, more convenient, and more well-developed than medieval cities, even though they are much larger and more polluted.

no doubt that humanity will find solutions to transportation, ecology and other problems in the future .

In one of its decisions, the United Nations Environmental and Social Council called the problem of urban development the most important problem facing humanity after maintaining peace on earth.

The famous Greek urbanist K. Doxia is said that "man has been defeated in the cities, if we do not find a new approach to the urban problem, then we will be doomed. "Architects, geographers, economists, demographers and representatives of many other disciplines are dealing with the problems of big cities and urbanism, all of them are thrown into one stream, only from different parts of the coast," he said.

What are the essence, main concepts and most acute problems of modern urbanism?

Urbanization - (Latin *urbs* - city) is a multifaceted worldwide socio-economic process related to the development and accumulation of productive forces, forms of social relations, the spread of the urban lifestyle to all aspects of the population's habitat. Any narrow understanding of this word, i.e. the growth of cities and urban population, the increase in the share of urban population in the total population, etc., is not sufficient to describe it. The increase in the number of cities and the population of the city can also occur in the decrease of the population of the city. A country or region can be contrasted with their level of urbanization, that is, the share of urban population in the whole population system does not increase, but the level of urbanization is high, while developing countries, on the contrary, the level of urban population can be low.

Urbanization is the process of increasing importance of the city in the development of society.

Signs of urbanization are the growth of industry in cities, the development of their cultural and political functions, deepening of the regional division of labor. Another sign of urbanization is the influx of rural residents to cities, the intensification of the pendulum movement of people from surrounding villages and small towns to large cities.

"False urbanization" is the gradual pulling of rural migrants into the orbit of the city, the long preservation of the old way of life in the vast "poverty areas" formed around the cities of many developing countries.

"Closing urbanization" is an unexpected process at first glance. Recent US studies show a slight decline in urban population. Financially well-off groups of the city are moving to the suburbs to be closer to nature, away from the noise of the city, and service groups are also spreading to the suburbs, and the urban system is becoming fragmented.

"Urban agglomeration" comes from the Latin word *agglomerate* - to join, to merge. In production technology, agglomeration means "creating large lumps from small ore and powdery materials by melting".

In ecological literature, the word "agglomeration" refers to the territorial integration of industrial enterprises in one place.

In a certain sense, this word also refers to the formation of associations that differ in form and structure through the accumulation and merging of residential areas. Convergence of agglomerations under the influence of development and accumulation of production leads to the formation of *megacities*.

Megapolises are urbanized zones covering large areas. (A megalopolis has emerged in the USA between Boston and Washington along the Atlantic coast).

The population of Tashkent agglomeration (Tashkent, Chirchik, Yangiyol) is 2.8 million. constitutes a person.

The population of Fergana agglomeration (Fergana, Margilan, Kegeili) is 350 is a thousand people.

According to the UN analysis in 1950, there were two megacities in the world: 12.3 mln. New York with a population of 11.3 million. populated Tokyo. In 1975, Mexico City joined them (Tokyo - 26.6 million inhabitants, New York - 15.9 million inhabitants, Mexico City - 10.7 million inhabitants). By 2025, their number will reach 27, and 21 of them will be located in developed countries. In cities with more than 10 million inhabitants, the population increased from 53 to 286 million in 1975-2007, and it is expected to increase to 447 million by 2025.

Tokyo has a special place among megacities (population 35.7 million people in 2007). It covers Greater Tokyo and 87 surrounding cities. These include urban centers that have their own distinct legal status, such as Yokohama, Kawasaki, and Chibu.

After Tokyo, there are agglomerations of New York, Mexico City and Bombay (each with more than 19 million inhabitants), as well as Sao Paulo (18.8).

In 2007, the largest number of megacities were on the Asian continent, eleven of them. There were four megacities in Latin America, and one each in Africa and Europe.

In recent years, the rapid growth of cities has been called the "urbanization revolution" in scientific literature. According

to estimates, more than half of the planet's population lives in cities in 2005. Modern demographic conditions show that two-thirds of the world's urban population is 65 million people every year. live in developing cities that are getting new residents. According to UN estimates, the level of urbanization in developing countries may reach 80% in 2025.

CONCLUSIONS

A different microclimate is formed in megacities. Residential buildings reduce wind speed, and stagnant air causes the accumulation of harmful industrial gases. Smog is a mixture of dust, smoke and fog that reduces sunlight and causes serious diseases in people. The temperature of the city is always higher than the temperature of this geographical area.

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